

Queue-Time Prediction

Anto Joseph
Department of Computer Application
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirappally, India
antojoseph2022a@mca.ajce.in

Pauline Paul
Department of Computer Application
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering Kanjirappally, India
paulinepaul@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract— One of the primary difficulties that hospitals confront nowadays is patient overpopulation. Unnecessary and inconvenient long-term delays waste a lot of human resources and time, and they make patients even more frustrated. The cumulative treatment time of all the patients in front of him determines how long each patient must wait. Patients would find it more convenient and preferable if they could receive the most efficient treatment plan and be informed of the estimated waiting time via a mobile application that updated in real time. A Queue Time Prediction system is designed based on the projected waiting time, which calculates and predicts an efficient and convenient time plan for the patient. The proposed system predicts the accurate time of patients based on the consulting average time.

Keywords—Time prediction based on average time, predicted call time, Emergency time.

I. INTRODUCTION

The main issues that hospitals faced is the patient wait times and congestion. The patient must undergo several examinations, inspections, or tests, which are usually dictated by his medical condition. Similarly, there are a lot of reasons for a patient to complete his hospital stay as quickly as feasible. It is necessary to maintain excellent queue management in order to facilitate the fast-track treatment process. However, because each patient requires distinct phases of treatment and operations such as check-ups, patient queue management and wait time prediction pose obstacles and complications.

Queue Time Prediction (QTP) is used to categorize the patients based on the average time. Furthermore, this implementation is applied to Time Prediction for each patient. This is where technology comes into scenario developing system to overcome the queue management and providing effective patient waiting time for each treatment using Apache for real time data analysis using Hypertext Preprocessor scripting language.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

When confronted with information streams coupling unknown dynamics, such as regular and unexpected occupation coasts, SAIRT [1] uses the stimulating representation to revolutionize the convinced constituency of the occupation, noise, and effective coast. Tyree [2] proposes a new method for parallelizing GBRT training, which is now the state-of-the-art knowledge standard for machine-learned network investigate ranking. Information mining is a new field in computer science with a wide range of applications. Its goal is to extract information from massive amounts of data in a human-readable way. In the

datamining field, decision trees [3], as well as a new, high-presentation, system-intensity planning for the CART algorithm, are the most important and widely used algorithms. Yael Ben-Haim [4] provides a novel method for building decision tree classifiers, sometimes known as DTCs. The algorithm works in a dispersed environment and is especially useful for categorizing large data sets and streaming data. It is pragmatically exposed to be as precise as a traditional DTC, while also being individually scalable for the benefit of streaming data across many mainframes. ' is a tree forecaster that requires each tree in the woods to rely on the criteria of a random vector illustration independently and with the same allotment for each and every one of them. The addition of a collection of trees, allowing them to choose for the most popular class, has resulted in a significant improvement in classification accuracy. To create these ensembles, random vectors are generated on a regular basis that administer the augmentation of each tree in the ensemble [5]. Curtis et al., Curtis et al., Curtis et al (2018;) Long waiting times are linked to patient annoyance, anger, anxiety, and discontent, according to Sun et al. (2000) and Ward et al. (2017) studies. [5]. An RF is created to generate discriminative ballots from entity curiosity points in a professional manner, and a top-K sub-level examination method is used to locate all active illustrations in a certain search area. Such a top-K investigation can achieve on down-sampled gain volumes for supplemental resourceful localization without significantly degrading the presentation. [6].

III. METHODOLOGY

The purpose of this paper is to find how much time the patient must wait in the queue for the treatment. Proposed system is able find the exact time that the patient must wait in the queue. Precise processing flow of the proposed system is depicted in figure 1.

Multiple steps were undertaken to analyze, and finalize the data:

Step 1: Based on the previous data we find the average value that taken by the doctor to examine the patients.

Step 2: Used Step 1 to predict the time to consult the doctor.

Step 3: Time changes to all patients according to the calling of patients by the doctor and the time constantly updating in the application.

PROCESSING STEPS

Predict the time from the average before the consultation time

step : 1

calculate the average time based on the previous data.

avg=total patients consulting time / total number of patients.

step : 2

calculate the consulting time of each patients from average

time=(avg*token number)+consulting time

```
$s13=mysqli_query($co,"SELECT avgtime,ctime,emtime  
FROM `deptdoctors` WHERE doctid=$did");
```

```
if($r1=mysqli_fetch_assoc($s13))
```

```
{  
    $avgtime1=$r1['avgtime'];  
    $startTime=$r1['ctime'];  
    $emtime=$r1['emtime'];  
}  
$mi=$tk-1;//get the difference in tokenno  
$mul=$mi*$avgtime1;  
$convertedTime=date('H:i:s',strtotime('+'. $mul.'minutes',,  
strtotime($startTime)));
```

Updating the time of each patient by the doctor

condition 1: Doctor calling out patients before the consulting time

step: 1

reduced time = predicted time - calling time

The time is reducing from all other patients wait for the consulting

```
//minus all time
```

```
$ca=abs($ca);  
$w1=mysqli_query($con,"SELECT * from doctpatients  
WHERE waitlist='0' and doctid='$did'");  
while($ro1=mysqli_fetch_assoc($w1))  
{  
    $s=$ro1['pcalltime'];  
    $convertedTime=date('H:i:s',strtotime('-'. $ca.  
'seconds',strtotime($s)));  
    $oo=$ro1['opno'];  
    $w12=mysqli_query($con,"UPDATE `doctpatients` SET  
    `pcalltime`='$convertedTime' WHERE opno='$oo'");  
}
```

condition 2: Doctor calling out patients after the consulting time

step: 1

incremented time = predicted time - calling time

The time is incremented from all other patients wait for the consulting

```
//plus all time
```

```
$ca=abs($ca);
```

```
$w1=mysqli_query($con,"SELECT * from doctpatients  
WHERE waitlist='0' and doctid='$did'");
```

```
while($ro1=mysqli_fetch_assoc($w1))
```

```
{  
    $s=$ro1['pcalltime'];  
    $convertedTime=date('H:i:s',strtotime('+'. $ca.  
'seconds',strtotime($s)));  
    $oo=$ro1['opno']; $w12=mysqli_query($con,"UPDATE  
    `doctpatients` SET `pcalltime`='$convertedTime' WHERE  
    opno='$oo'");  
}
```

Updating emergency time to all patients

Receive emergency time from the doctor

Time=patients predicted calling time + emergency time

when the patient take appointment in between the consulting time ,emergency time is added with the predicted time.

```
$ca=$_POST['eme'];
```

```
$q1=mysqli_query($con,"SELECT `emtime` FROM  
`deptdoctors` WHERE doctid='$did'");
```

```
$q2=mysqli_fetch_assoc($q1);
```

```
$t11=$q2['emtime'];
```

```
$sec=strtotime($ca)-strtotime('00:00:00');
```

```
$convertedTime=date('H:i:s',strtotime('+'. $sec.'seconds',strtotime($t11)));
```


Figure: 1

IV. EXPERIMENT RESULT ANALYSIS

Figure: 2

In figure 2 we plot the deviation of predicted time and the doctor calling time. If the predicted time and calling time are accurate then we get a straight line as the result. The occurrence of variation in the graph is because of two or more feature such as doctors calling before or after the predicted time or because of the emergency time.

doctid	Integer
--------	---------

opno	Integer
tokenno	Integer
waitlist	Integer
pcalltime	Time
calltime	Time

Table: 1

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have explored how we can precisely predict the waiting time in hospital queues. There are some factors affecting the efficiency of the system such as absents of patients after booking, customized attending time taken by the doctor for the individual patients, also, in addition one of the most challenging factors is the occurrence of unexpected emergency cases where the doctors would have to be away from attending the patients. For an efficient modelling with precision, it requires the emergency time to be considered, as it occurs to be updated for the exact prediction of the updated queue time. In the present models or existing system, such unexpected events are not considered and it affects the accuracy and efficiency of the system to a great extent, which is solved by incorporating the real time variable such as average value taken from the consulting time and the emergency time variable.

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